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Effects of Open Science

We collected hypothesized pathways through which openness might lead to better science. Specifically, we investigated the proposed causal effects of sharing scientific results, collected data, analysis code as well as study materials on changes in trustworthiness and breadth of the scientific literature. *2nd order certainty* refers to knowledge about the correctness of the investigatory process besides the known statistical certainty, such as computational correctness.

Proposed pathways

- sharing data/code → verifiable → increased responsibility and double-checking before sharing ([Purić et al., 2019](#))
- sharing data/code → better data curation standards ([Purić et al., 2019](#))
- sharing data → aggregation and secondary analyses ([Purić et al., 2019](#))
- sharing data/materials → reuse, leading to increased productivity ([Vazire, 2018](#))
- sharing code → less reinventions needed → higher productivity ([Purić et al., 2019](#), but contrary evidence from [Tiokhin, Yan, & Morgan](#))
- sharing data → preservation/less data loss ([Banks et al., 2019](#))
- sharing data/code → third parties can check scope, generalizability and replicability ([Purić et al., 2019](#), [Prike, 2022](#))
- sharing materials → direct replication becomes easier ([Prike, 2022](#))
- sharing paper → more scientific breakthroughs ([Purić et al., 2019](#))
- sharing paper → transfer of knowledge ([Hopf et al., 2022](#))
- sharing paper → quality (no evidence: [Hopf et al., 2022](#))
- sharing paper → productivity (mixed evidence: [Hopf et al., 2022](#))
- sharing data/paper → higher probability that other scientists can detect mistakes ([Frankenhuis & Nettle, 2018](#))
- sharing data/paper → higher probability that other scientists gain more insight into the data ([Frankenhuis & Nettle, 2018](#))
- thorough reporting of all studies run, data exclusions, and robustness to alternative analytic models → ? ([Vazire, 2018](#))

Causal model

